

DIVIDEND ANNOUNCEMENTS AND THEIR IMPACT ON EQUITIES LISTED IN NATIONAL STOCK EXCHANGE: AN EVENT STUDY

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Abstract

The dynamism of National Stock Exchange has been tested in the present research considering the equities listed in its 11 sectoral indices comprised of 142 companies. Event Study methodology had been adapted in the present research to check the existence of abnormal returns on account of dividend announcements. All dividend announcements made by the selected companies during 2015-16 to 2021-22 has been considered for this study. Outcomes of the present study with its AARs and CAARs confirm that the Indian Stock Market is not efficient and investors can get abnormal return with in three days on account of dividend announcement.

Keywords: Event Study, Dividend Announcement, Abnormal Return, National Stock Exchange, Indian Stock Market, Efficient Market Hypothesis

Introduction

Corporate Announcement can be defined as the information disseminated to the shareholders and general public by the corporate houses. Product launch, disclosing of financial statements, error in the financial reports, change in the board members, employees layoff, merger / amalgamation / acquisition, declaration of dividend, declaration of rights issue, declaration of bonus issue, declaration of stock split, share buyback, etc. which expresses the present and future projections of the company to the market. The announcements may be positive or negative to the shareholders / general public. When market notices the announcement as positive information, it immediately reflects on the equities by influencing the share price & traded volume positively, vice versa. Though the information disseminated to the shareholders and general public via media, it never reaches them instantly and confirms that market is imperfect where all information never reaches the target audience instantly (Prabakaran, Krishnaveni, & Shamini, 2019). Semi-strong form of Efficient Market Hypothesis suggests that a person who receives information earlier will react quickly in the stock market and get benefit out of it. It is evident that not all information influences the company's share price and traded volume either positively or negatively (Prabakaran & Ganesan, 2016). Few may influence and many may not. Hence, one should have a deep understanding to play with the corporate announcements on the equities. The present study is proposed considering the need and importance of corporate event announcements and their impact on the equities.

Research Questions

- What kind of impact does the announcement of dividend creates on the company's share price?
- How to perceive information as positive or negative to the market?
- Does all information influence the stock price?, further, how to predict the depth of impact on the stock price?

The present study primarily intended to answer the above research questions by analysing the dividend announcements and their impact on stocks listed in National Stock Exchange, using Event Study as a tool.

Objectives of the study

- To understand the level of impact made by the dividend announcements as an event on the share price and traded volume of companies listed in NSE Sectoral Indices.
- Using Event Study methodology to figure out the Average Abnormal Return on account of dividend announcements.

Scope of the study

- Scope of study is the complete enumeration of dividend announcements by the selected 162 companies during the study period [01.04.2015 to 31.03.2022].
- Despite the availability of numerous corporate announcements, only dividend announcement is considered as event for the present research, since the dividend announcement is directly linked with the monetary benefits for the investors.
- The significant impact on equity price and volume traded during the event window is tested and the data pertaining to event date, equity price and volume traded are downloaded from the official website of National Stock Exchange [www.nseindia.com]

Research Methodology

Sectoral indices are the true representatives of the industry / sector's movement. National Stock Exchange has 15 sectoral indices, (National Stock Exchange, 2022) and out of which 11 sectoral indices are selected for this study namely, Nifty Auto Index, Nifty Bank Index, Nifty Consumer Durables Index, Nifty Financial Services Index, Nifty FMCG Index, Nifty Healthcare Index, Nifty IT Index, Nifty Media Index, Nifty Metal Index, Nifty Oil & Gas Index and Nifty Realty Index. Nifty Private Bank Index, Nifty PSU Bank Index, Nifty Pharma Index and Nifty Financial Services 25/50 Index are not considered for this study as most of the companies listed in these indices are already covered in those selected indices. All dividend announcements made by 142 listed members / companies constituted in the above sectoral indices are considered for this present research during the financial year from 2015-16 to 2021-22.

The significant impact of dividend announcements on equity price and volume is tested using Event Study methodology, where dividend announcement is considered as the event for the study. Ten days have been considered as the event window includes five days prior to announcements and five days from the date of event announcements. In order to forecast the abnormal return during event window, 100 days are considered as the estimation period. Paired sample t test is used in this study to test the significant difference between pre and post event days.

Steps for Event Study

- **Event day:** It is the foremost responsibility of the researcher to identify the event and it is marked as announcement date. The announcement date or event date is earmarked as “Day 0”.
- **Time Line:** Typical time line of event study includes event window [pre-event days & post event days] and estimation period.

Where

T_0 is the Event Day (ED) or Day 0

T_{-5} to T_0 is the Pre Event Days

T_0 to T_5 is the Post Event Days

T_{-100} to T_{-5} is the Estimation Period

- **Estimate the expected return:** The return expected is used as yardstick to relate with actual return during the event window, (Prabakaran & Krishnaveni, 2019). The abnormal return can be estimated considering actual return and expected return as base values. Following are the most acceptable models in the financial market to track the expected return.
 1. Mean Adjusted Return
 2. Market Adjusted Return
 3. Market Model Adjusted Return
 4. CAPM Adjusted Return

This study has adopted the Market Model Adjusted Return to track the expected return during the event window.

$$E(R_{i,t}) = \alpha_i + \beta_i R_{m,t} \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

α , β are estimated using Least Square Regression method over the estimated period.

$E(R_{i,t})$ - Expected stock return at time period t

$R_{m,t}$ - Market return at time period t

- **Computing Abnormal Return (AR)**

An abnormal return can be estimated considering actual return and expected return as base. Following is the formula used to estimate the abnormal return for an event.

$$AR_{i,t} = R_{i,t} - E(R_{i,t}) \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

- **Computing Cumulative Abnormal Return (CAR)**

$$CAR (T_1, T_2) = \sum_{T=-T_1}^{T_2} AR_{i,t} \quad \text{----- (3)}$$

The number of listed members in each sectoral index is presented below which was taken from the official website of National Stock Exchange.

Table 1: Listed Members of Sectoral Indices

S. No	Sector	No. of Listed Members
1	Automobile	15
2	Banking	12
3	Consumer Durables	15
4	Financial Services	20
5	FMCG	15
6	Healthcare	20
7	IT	10
8	Media	10
9	Metal	15
10	Oil & Gas	15
11	Realty	10
Total		142

Limitations of the study

- The present study is carried out considering the impact of dividend announcement on equity price and volume traded. The impact of other events during the study period is considered as negligible or ignored.
- Numerous studies have been carried out considering different event windows and estimation periods. However, the present research is considering the event window as ten days and 100 days estimation period, which is the pure outcome of the literature review carried out. The result of this study may vary for different event windows and different estimation periods.

Review of Literature

Present study is the inspirational outcomes of (Fama, Fisher, Jensen, & Roll, 1969) who were the pioneer in the event study methodology. Initially the event study methodology was used to estimate the abnormal return for stock split announcements considering event window ± 30 days. (Ball & Brown, 1968) Were the first person who suggested modification in the existing event study methodology. The study indicated the biased in the coefficient of estimates, if event period is encompassed while estimating the market model parameters. As a result of external influences, the exact impact made by an event cannot be measured using market model adjusted return. (Gonedes, 1973) Suggested to use monthly stock price instead of years. However, (Scholes, 1972) used the Market Model Adjusted Return earlier to event announcements and tracked the abnormal returns for event window.

Semi strong form of Indian stock market was tested by (Mandal & Rao, 2010) considering dividend announcement as the event. The research was carried out with 40 dividend announcements and 44 dividend omissions by companies constituted under BSE 500. ± 10 days were considered as event window and the study found the existence of 1.4% Average Abnormal Return due to dividend announcements and 2% due to dividend omissions. Finally the study concludes by confirming the semi-strong form of Indian stock market towards dividend announcements.

Similarly, (Saravanakumar, 2011) conducted a research considering 50 companies constituted under NSE Nifty indice with ± 4 days as event window. The study concludes by confirming the existence of positive reaction to dividend announcements, however, magnitude of the impact depends on the magnitude of the announcements. Both the studies reveal similar result, where, the investors perceives dividend announcements as positive signal and it immediately reflects on its share price. However, the decreased dividend values, reflects negatively.

Supporting the above, (Zafar, Chaubey, & Khalid, 2012) and (Gupta, Dogra, Vashisht, & Ghai, 2012) have conducted similar kind of studies with dividend announcements as event. Both the studies have taken samples from National Stock Exchange and Bombay Stock Exchange respectively, and used event study methodology to identify the existence of Abnormal Return.

Contrary to the above, the research carried out by (Sharma & Renuka, 2011) and (Ramachandran, 2013) reveals that the Indian Stock Market is efficient and further in favour of semi-strong form of Efficient Market Hypothesis. In both the studies, the samples are the companies listed under Bombay Stock Exchange and they have considered ± 11 days and ± 30 days as event window respectively. The event study methodology failed to prove the existence of Abnormal Return on account of dividend announcements and by concludes that the dividend announcements cannot support in generating abnormal return by the investors.

Numerous studies have been carried out in the field of stock market and they have used event study methodology to assess the Abnormal Return. Despite numerous studies, the results are contradicting, and could not find any consistency. This may be due to differences in samples, time line, events and its magnitude, etc. The present researchers wish to assess the efficiency of Indian Stock Market at this moment by using event study methodology. However, no studies have been carried out considering all sectoral indices listed under National Stock Exchange. Also the event window of ± 5 days was not taken by any researchers for their research work. Considering the research gap mentioned above, the present study is defined the objective by assessing the impact of dividend announcements on equities [share price and traded volume] for a specified period of time line.

Analysis & Inference

Daily returns of equities during event window are considered as the base for calculating Abnormal Return. Since, the equity prices for all companies are not same and to make the platform common for all, their daily returns are used as the base for the paired sample t test. Similarly, percentage change in the volume traded during event window for all companies are considered for applying paired sample t test. The Abnormal Returns during event window for a company at different time line are calculated, averaged and named as Average Abnormal Return. The outcomes of paired sample t test applied on equity price, volume traded and Average Abnormal Returns are displayed sectoral indices wise as given below.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under Automobile Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	Ashok Leyland Ltd.	0.512*	0.262	-3.440**
2	Bajaj Auto Ltd.	0.134*	-0.101	-4.670**
3	Balkrishna Industries Ltd.	-0.017**	-0.124	-2.370**
4	Bharat Forge Ltd.	-0.814*	-0.875	3.120**
5	Bosch Ltd.	-0.124*	0.168	-7.678**
6	Eicher Motors Ltd.	-0.265**	-0.194	-6.328**
7	Escorts Kubota Ltd.	0.501*	0.037	4.270**
8	Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	0.609*	-0.484	-3.174**
9	MRF Ltd.	0.612	-0.475	2.414**
10	Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	-0.046	0.067	-4.942
11	Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	0.071*	-0.194	3.673**
12	Sona BLW Precision Forgings Ltd.	0.209*	-0.840	-4.074**
13	TVS Motor Company Ltd.	0.320*	-0.064	-5.127**
14	Tata Motors Ltd.	0.224**	-0.727	-6.792**
15	Tube Investments of India Ltd.	0.161	-0.260	4.751

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX Auto Indice. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. Significant mean differences on daily returns were not observed on companies such as MRF Ltd., Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd. and Tube Investments of India Ltd. However, there is no evident of significant volume traded during event window for all companies. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies except, Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd. and Tube Investments of India Ltd.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under Bank Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	AU Small Finance Bank Ltd.	0.184*	-0.667	-6.279**
2	Axis Bank Ltd.	0.294*	-0.981	4.576**
3	Bandhan Bank Ltd.	0.654**	-0.767	8.798**
4	Bank of Baroda	-0.334	-0.450	8.982**
5	Federal Bank Ltd.	-0.885	0.743	-4.974
6	HDFC Bank Ltd.	0.574**	0.029	3.745**
7	ICICI Bank Ltd.	0.127*	-0.037	-3.241**
8	IDFC First Bank Ltd.	0.374*	-0.275	7.766**
9	IndusInd Bank Ltd.	-0.094*	-0.661	-1.998**
10	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	-0.324**	-0.216*	11.777**
11	Punjab National Bank	0.064	-0.617*	9.879**
12	State Bank of India	0.374**	-0.227	-3.358**

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX Bank Indice. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. Significant mean differences on daily returns were not observed on companies such as Bank of Baroda, Federal Bank Ltd. and Punjab National Bank. However, the significant impact on traded volume was observed only in two companies namely, Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd. and Punjab National Bank. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies except, Federal Bank Ltd.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under Consumer Durable Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	Amber Enterprises India Ltd.	0.365*	-0.264	5.726**
2	Bata India Ltd.	1.423	0.473	1.622
3	Blue Star Ltd.	-0.191	0.081	-2.695
4	Crompton Greaves Consumer Electricals Ltd.	0.724*	-0.694	2.109**
5	Dixon Technologies (India) Ltd.	-0.295**	-0.684	2.075**
6	Havells India Ltd.	0.075*	-0.167	3.874**
7	Kajaria Ceramics Ltd.	-0.034**	-0.282	4.832*
8	Orient Electric Ltd.	0.464*	-0.083	-9.295**
9	Rajesh Exports Ltd.	-0.317*	0.994	-7.077
10	Relaxo Footwears Ltd.	0.064*	0.078	-6.023**
11	TTK Prestige Ltd.	-0.708*	-0.398	-10.804**
12	Titan Company Ltd.	-0.194	0.475	-4.703
13	V-Guard Industries Ltd.	0.073*	0.568	-2.289**
14	Voltas Ltd.	-0.180**	-0.371	-2.792**
15	Whirlpool of India Ltd.	-0.473	-0.262	4.376

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX Consumer Durable Indice. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. Significant mean differences on daily returns were not observed on companies such as Bata India Ltd., Blue Star Ltd., Titan Company Ltd. and Whirlpool of India Ltd. However, there is no evident of significant volume traded during event window for all companies. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies except, Bata India Ltd., Blue Star Ltd., Rajesh Exports Ltd., Titan Company Ltd. and Whirlpool of India Ltd.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under Finance Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	Axis Bank Ltd.	0.294*	-0.981	4.576**
2	Bajaj Finance Ltd.	-0.361**	-0.383	5.275**
3	Bajaj Finserv Ltd.	-0.082**	-0.467	5.964**
4	Cholamandalam Investment and Finance Company Ltd.	-0.118*	-1.582	-7.070**
5	HDFC Asset Management Company Ltd.	-0.029*	-0.791	7.534**
6	HDFC Bank Ltd.	0.574**	0.029	3.745**
7	HDFC Life Insurance Company Ltd.	0.324	-2.82**	4.475**
8	Housing Development Finance Corporation Ltd.	0.034*	0.575	2.388
9	ICICI Bank Ltd.	0.127*	-0.037	-3.241**
10	ICICI Lombard General Insurance Company Ltd.	0.261	-0.482	-2.573
11	ICICI Prudential Life Insurance Company Ltd.	1.443*	0.167	2.934**
12	Indian Energy Exchange Ltd.	-0.228*	-1.281	4.675**
13	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	-0.324**	-0.216*	11.777**
14	Muthoot Finance Ltd.	0.176**	-0.638	6.294**
15	Power Finance Corporation Ltd.	0.296*	-0.995*	3.417**
16	REC Ltd.	0.088**	-0.667	-6.485**
17	SBI Cards and Payment Services Ltd.	0.277*	0.082	4.579**
18	SBI Life Insurance Company Ltd.	-0.162	-0.564*	-2.592
19	Shriram Transport Finance Co. Ltd.	0.224*	-0.582	3.024**
20	State Bank of India	0.374**	-0.227	-3.358**

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX Finance Indice. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. Significant mean differences on daily returns were not observed on companies such as HDFC Life Insurance Company Ltd., ICICI Lombard General Insurance Company Ltd. and SBI Life Insurance Company Ltd. However, the significant impact of volume traded was observed in few companies namely, HDFC Life Insurance Company Ltd., Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd., Power Finance Corporation Ltd. and SBI Life Insurance Company Ltd. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies except, Housing Development Finance Corporation Ltd., ICICI Lombard General Insurance Company Ltd. and SBI Life Insurance Company Ltd.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under FMCG Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	Britannia Industries Ltd.	0.375*	-0.261	-1.584*
2	Colgate Palmolive (India) Ltd.	1.182**	-1.234	-6.584**
3	Dabur India Ltd.	0.634**	0.267	4.178**
4	Emami Ltd.	0.161*	-1.482*	-3.894**
5	Godrej Consumer Products Ltd.	0.676*	-0.261	-2.584**
6	Hindustan Unilever Ltd.	0.268**	-0.662	2.394**
7	ITC Ltd.	-0.084*	-0.759	-0.181**
8	Marico Ltd.	-0.075*	-0.384	3.494**
9	Nestle India Ltd.	-0.098*	-0.434*	7.986**
10	Procter & Gamble Hygiene & Health Care Ltd.	-0.084*	-1.267	4.150**
11	Radico Khaitan Ltd	1.145**	-1.362	7.761**
12	Tata Consumer Products Ltd.	-0.46*	-0.584	-2.972**
13	United Breweries Ltd.	0.099**	0.067	-6.208**
14	United Spirits Ltd.	NA	NA	NA
15	Varun Beverages Ltd.	-0.186*	-0.297	-7.976**

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX FMCG Indice. United Spirits Ltd. has not made any dividend announcement during the study period and hence, not comes under this analysis part. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. However, the significant impact on volume traded was observed in two companies namely, Nestle India Ltd. and Emami Ltd. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies, since the t values are significant either at 1% or 5% level of significance.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under Healthcare Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	Abbott India Ltd.	0.513**	-0.999*	-3.140**
2	Alkem Laboratories Ltd.	-0.034**	-0.699	4.084**
3	Apollo Hospitals Enterprise Ltd.	-0.284*	0.082	-5.272**
4	Aurobindo Pharma Ltd.	0.297**	-0.475	-2.261**
5	Biocon Ltd.	0.181	-0.367	-1.346
6	Cipla Ltd.	0.564**	0.481	2.784**
7	Divi's Laboratories Ltd.	-0.135*	-0.967	9.967**
8	Dr. Lal Path Labs Ltd.	-0.281*	-0.206	6.061**
9	Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd.	0.064*	-0.282	5.882**
10	Glenmark Pharmaceuticals Ltd.	0.084*	-1.267	4.660**
11	Granules India Ltd.	0.437**	0.260	8.436**
12	Ipca Laboratories Ltd.	0.362**	0.350	-3.610**
13	Laurus Labs Ltd.	-0.508*	0.442	-2.173**
14	Lupin Ltd.	-0.260**	1.074	3.896*
15	Metropolis Healthcare Ltd.	0.291*	-0.067	9.367**
16	Pfizer Ltd.	-0.284*	-0.082	5.084**
17	Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd.	-0.086**	-1.497	-3.281**
18	Syngene International Ltd.	0.383**	0.067	3.994*
19	Torrent Pharmaceuticals Ltd.	0.072*	-0.328	7.584*
20	Zydus Lifesciences Ltd.	-0.160	-0.434*	5.072

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX Healthcare Indice. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. Significant mean differences on daily returns were not observed on companies such as Biocon Ltd. and Zydus Lifesciences Ltd. However, the significant impact on volume traded was observed in two companies namely, Abbott India Ltd. and Zydus Lifesciences Ltd. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies, except, Biocon Ltd. and Zydus Lifesciences Ltd., since the t values are not statistically significant.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under IT Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	Coforge Ltd.	0.442**	-0.372	2.494**
2	HCL Technologies Ltd.	-0.063*	-1.260	-7.480**
3	Infosys Ltd.	0.130**	-1.220	6.109**
4	L&T Technology Services Ltd.	-0.334	0.885	-4.840
5	Larsen & Toubro Infotech Ltd.	0.128**	-2.278	2.462**
6	MindTree Ltd.	-0.236**	-0.499	-6.672**
7	Mphasis Ltd.	0.361*	1.232	-4.360**
8	Tata Consultancy Services Ltd.	0.482*	0.244	5.881**
9	Tech Mahindra Ltd.	-0.337*	-0.677	3.461**
10	Wipro Ltd.	0.812*	-0.085	-2.681**

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX IT Indice. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. Significant mean difference on daily return was not observed from L&T Technology Services Ltd. However, there is no evident of significant volume traded during event window for all companies. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies, except, L&T Technology Services Ltd., since the t value is not statistically significant.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under Media Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	Dish TV India Ltd.	0.172*	-0.590	-2.364**
2	Hathway Cable & Datacom Ltd.	NA	NA	NA
3	Inox Leisure Ltd.	0.764**	0.322	-2.164**
4	Nazara Technologies Ltd.	NA	NA	NA
5	Network18 Media & Investments Ltd.	NA	NA	NA
6	PVR Ltd.	0.752**	0.442	-3.293**
7	Saregama India Ltd	0.374*	0.079	-4.473**
8	Sun TV Network Ltd.	0.223*	0.056	-1.243**
9	TV18 Broadcast Ltd.	NA	NA	NA
10	Zee Entertainment Enterprises Ltd.	0.116*	0.348	-0.551**

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX Media Indice. Hathway Cable & Datacom Ltd., Nazara Technologies Ltd., Network18 Media & Investments Ltd. and TV18 Broadcast Ltd. has not made any dividend announcements during the study period and hence, not comes under this analysis part. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there

exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. However, there is no evident of significant volume traded during event window for all companies. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies, since the t values are significant either at 1% or 5% level of significance.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under Metal Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	APL Apollo Tubes Ltd.	-0.025**	-0.014	-6.201**
2	Adani Enterprises Ltd.	0.741*	0.217	4.397**
3	Hindalco Industries Ltd.	0.849*	-0.304	-3.047**
4	Hindustan Copper Ltd.	0.852*	-0.295	2.541**
5	Hindustan Zinc Ltd.	0.194	0.247	-4.815
6	JSW Steel Ltd.	0.311*	-0.014	3.8**
7	Jindal Stainless Ltd.	0.449*	-0.66	-3.947**
8	Jindal Steel & Power Ltd.	0.56*	0.116	-5.000**
9	MOIL Ltd.	0.894**	-0.587	8.925**
10	National Aluminium Co. Ltd.	-0.094*	-0.27	9.109**
11	Ratnamani Metals & Tubes Ltd.	-0.645	0.923	-4.847
12	Steel Authority of India Ltd.	0.814*	0.209	3.872**
13	Tata Steel Ltd.	0.367*	0.143	-3.114**
14	Vedanta Ltd.	0.614*	-0.095	7.893**
15	Welspun Corp Ltd.	0.146	-0.481	-1.871**

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX Metal Indice. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. Significant mean differences on daily returns were not observed on few companies such as Hindustan Zinc Ltd., Ratnamani Metals & Tubes Ltd. and Welspun Corp Ltd. However, there is no evident of significant volume traded during event window for all companies. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies, except, Hindustan Zinc Ltd. and Ratnamani Metals & Tubes Ltd., since the t values are not statistically significant.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under Oil & Gas Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	Adani Total Gas Ltd.	-0.084*	-0.216*	11.904**
2	Aegis Logistics Ltd.	0.304*	-0.617*	10.006**
3	Bharat Petroleum Corporation Ltd.	0.964*	-0.514	2.236**
4	Castrol India Ltd.	-0.055**	-0.504	2.202**
5	GAIL (India) Ltd.	0.315**	0.013	4.001**
6	Gujarat Gas Ltd.	0.206**	-0.102	4.959*
7	Gujarat State Petronet Ltd.	0.704*	0.097	-9.168**
8	Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Ltd.	-0.077	1.174	-6.95
9	Indian Oil Corporation Ltd.	0.304*	0.258	-5.896**
10	Indraprastha Gas Ltd.	-0.468	-0.218	-10.677**
11	Mahanagar Gas Ltd.	0.046*	0.655	-4.576
12	Oil & Natural Gas Corporation Ltd.	0.313**	0.748	-2.162**
13	Oil India Ltd.	0.158**	-0.287	6.091**
14	Petronet LNG Ltd.	0.122**	-1.402	-6.943**
15	Reliance Industries Ltd.	0.211*	-0.611	7.661**

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX Oil & Gas Indice. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance. Significant mean differences on daily returns were not observed on few companies such as Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Ltd. and Indraprastha Gas Ltd. However, the significant impact on volume traded was observed in two companies namely, Adani Total Gas Ltd. and Aegis Logistics Ltd. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies, except, Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Ltd. and Mahanagar Gas Ltd., since the t values are not statistically significant.

Table: Impact of Dividend Announcements on Companies Listed Under Realty Indice

S.No	Listed Member	T Test [Equity Price]	T Test [Volume Traded]	T Test [AAA]
1	Brigade Enterprises Ltd.	0.128**	-0.620	-6.485**
2	DLF Ltd.	0.317*	0.129	4.579*
3	Godrej Properties Ltd.	-0.122*	-0.561	-2.592
4	Indiabulls Real Estate Ltd.	NA	NA	NA
5	Macrotech Developers Ltd.	NA	NA	NA
6	Oberoi Realty Ltd.	0.553*	-0.248	-3.14**
7	Phoenix Mills Ltd.	0.130*	-1.220	6.109**
8	Prestige Estates Projects Ltd.	1.182*	-1.234	-6.584**
9	Sobha Ltd.	0.634*	0.267	4.178**
10	Sunteck Realty Ltd.	1.443*	0.167	2.934**

*Significant at 1% LoS

**Significant at 5% LoS

The table above displays the outcomes of paired sample t test applied on the daily returns, traded volume and abnormal returns of stocks listed in CNX Realty Indices. Indiabulls Real Estate Ltd. and Macrotech Developers Ltd. have not made any dividend announcements during the study period and hence, not come under this analysis part. It is clearly evident from the paired sample t test that there exist significant mean differences on the stock daily returns between pre and post event announcements. The t values are significant either at 1% or at 5% level of significance for all companies listed under Realty Indices. However, there is no evidence of significant volume traded during event window. On the other hand, significant abnormal returns were observed between pre and post event announcements for all companies except, Godrej Properties Ltd.

Cumulative Average Abnormal Returns

In order to understand the significant impact on sectors wise, the Average Abnormal Returns of all events announced by companies listed in each sectoral indices are cumulated and presented in a graphical representation. For easy of understanding, three sectoral indices are compared in each figure as presented below.

Chart 1: CAARs in Automobile, Bank and Consumer Durable Sectors

The Chart 1 indicates the Cumulative Average Abnormal Returns [CAARs] due to dividend announcements on companies listed in Automobile, Banking and Consumer Durable sectors. It is very clear that there is a small amount of hike in cumulative average abnormal returns during post event announcements by companies listed in Automobile and Consumer Durable sectors. However, the hike is not withstanding for more than three days and after three days, it started declining. The CAARs of banking sectors shows a steady growth from pre-announcements to post announcements as indicated in the line chart.

Chart 2: CAARs in Financial Services, FMCG and Healthcare Sectors

The Chart 2 indicates the Cumulative Average Abnormal Returns [CAARs] due to dividend announcements on companies listed in Financial Services, FMCG and Healthcare sectors. It is very clear that there exists a hike in cumulative average abnormal returns during post event announcements by companies listed in Financial Services, FMCG and Healthcare sectors. However, the hike is not withstanding for more than three days and after three days, it started declining. Among three sectors, the highest magnitude during post event announcements was observed on companies listed in FMCG and Healthcare Sectors, as indicated in the peak value during T+1 and T+3 days respectively.

Chart 3: CAARs in IT, Media and Metal Sectors

The Chart 3 indicates the Cumulative Average Abnormal Returns [CAARs] due to dividend announcements on companies listed in IT, Media and Metal sectors. It is very clear that there exists a hike in cumulative average abnormal returns during post event announcements by companies listed in those sectors. However, the hike is not withstanding for more than a day

and afterwards, it started declining. Among three sectors, the highest magnitude during post event announcements was observed on companies listed in IT sector, as indicated in the peak value during T+1 day.

Chart 4: CAARs in Oil & Gas and Realty Sectors

The Chart 4 indicates the Cumulative Average Abnormal Returns [CAARs] due to dividend announcements on companies listed in Oil & Gas and Realty sectors. It is very clear that there exists a hike in cumulative average abnormal returns during post event announcements by companies listed in those sectors. However, the hike is not withstanding for more than a day and afterwards, it started declining. Among two sectors, the highest magnitude during post event announcements was observed on companies listed in Oil & Gas sector, as indicated in the peak value during T+1 day.

Discussion and Conclusion

Though the present study is complete enumeration of all dividend announcements made by 142 companies listed under different sectoral indices, few companies has not made any dividend announcements during the study period. Companies such as United Spirits Ltd. from FMCG Indice, Hathway Cable & Datacom Ltd., Nazara Technologies Ltd., Network18 Media & Investments Ltd. and TV18 Broadcast Ltd. from Media Indice and Indiabulls Real Estate Ltd. & Macrotech Developers Ltd. from Realty Indice are the companies without any dividend announcement.

Out of 135 companies declared dividend during the study period, the significant impact on stock daily returns was not observed in few companies such as, MRF Ltd., Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd., Tube Investments of India Ltd., Bank of Baroda, Federal Bank Ltd., Punjab National Bank, Bata India Ltd., Blue Star Ltd., Titan Company Ltd., Whirlpool of India Ltd., HDFC Life Insurance Company Ltd., ICICI Lombard General Insurance Company Ltd., SBI Life Insurance Company Ltd., Nestle India Ltd. and Emami Ltd., Biocon Ltd., Zydus Lifesciences Ltd., L&T Technology Services Ltd., Hindustan Zinc Ltd., Ratnamani Metals & Tubes Ltd., Welspun Corp Ltd., Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Ltd. and Indraprastha Gas

Ltd. This confirms that the dividend announcement has made significant difference between pre and post event announcements on equity daily returns for the identified companies.

However, the significant impact on volume traded during event window was observed in few companies such as, Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd., Punjab National Bank, HDFC Life Insurance Company Ltd., Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd., Power Finance Corporation Ltd., SBI Life Insurance Company Ltd., Emami Ltd., Nestle India Ltd., Abbott India Ltd., Zydus Lifesciences Ltd., Adani Total Gas Ltd. and Aegis Logistics Ltd.. This indicates that the dividend announcement has made significant difference between pre and post event announcements on traded volume for those mentioned companies.

The significant difference between pre and post event announcement with respect to Average Abnormal Return was observed in 103 companies. The Cumulative Average Abnormal Returns observed in the Automobile, Banking, Consumer Durable, Financial Services, FMCG and Healthcare sectors has a small amount of hike during post event announcements. However, the abnormal returns sustained only for three days. Similarly, the CAARs observed in IT, Media, Metal, Oil & Gas and Realty sectors has a hike during post event announcements, which is observed for a day. After the turnaround period, the CAARs have started declining.

From the detailed study, it is proved that the dividend announcement made by Indian companies has created a significant impact on their abnormal returns. However, the abnormality was observed in limited days; one to three days only. Hence, it is by concluding that the investors of National Stock Exchange has the opportunity to get abnormal return with in three days on account of dividend announcement which is the evident defines the weak form of Indian Stock market.

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